

MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH MANTLE CELL LYMPHOMA IN OLD PEOPLE ABOVE 60YEAR: NARRATIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Mantle cell lymphoma is an uncommon B-cell non-Hodgkin lymphoma with variable clinical and biochemical features. A very uncommon B-cell lymphoma exhibiting a distinctive immunophenotypic profile and a particular genetic abnormality is called mantle cell lymphoma. 65 is the median age. There is no medicine that can cure it; it is allogeneic. When making a diagnosis, risk stratification is essential. Mantle cell lymphoma therapy choices have increased significantly in recent years; in fact, elderly individuals who are unfit for routine treatment are at increased risk of toxicity. While the safety profiles of new medicines are generally good, older individuals who are not fit may experience unanticipated complications. Hematologists may be able to address these vulnerabilities by involving geriatricians and conducting a complete geriatric evaluation in medical treatment. Most of the time, for patients.

Keywords: Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma, Mantle Cell Lymphoma, Chemotherapy drug, Immunotherapy drug.

INTRODUCTION

Blood malignancies that originate in the lymphatic system are referred to as "lymphomas." Although it's a dangerous condition, medical professionals can effectively treat and frequently even cure it. Non-Hodgkin lymphoma isn't a single disease. There exist numerous varieties of non-Hodgkin lymphoma. There are several common forms of aggressive non-Hodgkin lymphomas [1]. These are lymphomas that progress or spread very quickly and cause more serious symptoms than indolent non-Hodgkin lymphomas. When given treatment, they usually react promptly.

- *Aggressive B-cell lymphomas*

1. Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL)
2. lymphoma
3. Lymphoblastic lymphoma
4. Burkett lymphoma

- *Mantle cell Aggressive T-cell and NK lymphoma*

1. Peripheral T-cell lymphoma (PTCL)
2. Angioimmunoblastic T-cell lymphoma (AITL)
3. Systematic large cell lymphoma (ALCL)
4. Hepatosplenic gamma/delta T-cell lymphoma

Mantle cell lymphoma is a subtype of non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL) [1,13].

According to the WHO classification, a developed B-cell malignancy is called mantle cell lymphoma (MCL). that is often made up of small to medium-sized, monomorphic lymphoid cells possessing irregular nuclei. There are no paraimmunoblasts, pseudofollicles, or centroblasts present [2]. The tumor cells often co-express CD5 and have a B-cell characteristic. This type happens when a B-cell is located in the so-called mantle zone. Your lymph nodes are where the WBCs that cause mantle cell lymphoma begin their journey. Mantle cell lymphoma has no known cure, yet there are therapies that can put the illness into remission [1]. In order to extend the duration of remission, physicians and researchers are creating novel therapies as well as innovative applications for already-approved ones [3]. Within MCL therapy, the term "elderly" is ill-defined; pragmatic cutoffs for calculating the resistance to the intensity of treatment, between 60 and 70 years old in different research studies, are frequently used in clinical trials [4]. However, exceptions and limitations to this definition are well-recognized in real-world clinical practice; for instance, patients with comorbidities under 65 years old are frequently considered for less-intensive treatment, while some patients well into their 70s do quite well with high-dose therapy in conjunction with stem cell transplant [5,6]. Ultimately, effective treatment customized to individual risk profiles and widely applicable to all patients will reduce the influence of age on treatment decisions while offering the potential to improve quality of life and patient satisfaction [1,8,9].

The condition MCL affects the body: Where do the stars form B-cells located on lymph nodes in the mantle zone? It often begins with indolent behavior that later becomes aggressive [10]. Cancer spreads from lymph nodes to the bloodstream, bone marrow, and digestive system at later phases of the development of the disease.

Serious mantle cell lymphoma, etiology

Mantle cell lymphoma MCL is not a common disease, but it is sporadic. It is uncommon, impacting 1 in 2,00,000 persons. Most commonly seen in people aged 60 to 70. Compared to women (DFAB), this condition is more likely to develop in men (DMAB). DMAB (designated male at birth) and DFAB (designated female at birth) And men's are 3 to 1, which means that in 10 people, about 1 with MCL, a subtype of NHL, has a version of a slow-growing condition. But immediate treatment is required in most cases of aggressive behavior [4,11]. The majority of the time, therapy can result in remission. Regrettably, remission from MCL does not equate to a complete recovery from cancer. After months or years of remission, MCL might recur [12].

Cause of MCL: The risk of developing the disease is slightly higher with age, sex, family history, lower immunity, and infections. [13]. The majority of the time, B cell function is altered by gene mutations. Cyclin D1, a protein that promotes B cell growth, is produced in excess by abnormal B cells. The excessively high level of cyclin D1 causes B cells to proliferate and duplicate. Tumors caused by the duplicate cells develop into lymphomas. [14,2]. It is unknown to researchers what causes this genetic alteration. However, utilizing genetic analysis, healthcare providers can diagnose MCL and develop treatment.

Signs and indications of MCL: Has many common physical symptoms; you may not be aware that these are cancer signs. That's why the majority of individuals were diagnosed with non-Hodgkin lymphoma at that time. As distinct indicators of B-cell lymphoma, certain symptoms are recognized by medical professionals as B symptoms. Night sweats, persistent fevers, OTC medications, and inexplicable weight loss are examples of these B symptoms [1,15]. 10% of body weight in 6 months without following any workout or diet regimens. Additional signs and symptoms include heartburn, nausea, vomiting, or diarrhea; increased neck lymph nodes, armpits, or groin; abdominal pain or bloating; enlarged spleen and tonsils; hepatomegaly; weariness; and lower back strain or ache[16] .

Management and treatment:

Therapy is determined by the particular circumstances; some may have MCL with no signs for that type of case, and providers suggest the option of watchful waiting. Usually, health care providers use the combination chemotherapy and immunotherapy drug rituximab [17,18] as first-line or primary care. For older and fit individuals, initial treatment with traditional patient-based immunotherapy is the main course of treatment. The combination of rituximab with benamustine (BR) or doxorubicin, vincristine, and prednisone (R-CHOP) [19] offers a median overall survival (OS) of more than seven years, with a median progression-free survival (PFS) of three to five years. Additionally, targeted therapy that uses antibodies like ibrutinib to destroy particular cancer cells is called monoclonal antibody therapy. MCL cannot be cured by autologous stem cell transplantation. Prior to stem cell transplantation, severe chemotherapy is required [9]. Steroids, which make chemotherapy more effective [20], Radiotherapy, as well as high-energy rays, does vanquish the cell, and this treatment may also affect neighboring healthy cells. This therapy is employed to address relief, pain-like symptoms, or stages I and II. Following the initial chemotherapy response, suitable patients get high-dose therapy and then have a transfusion of autologous stem cells. Rituximab maintenance is administered for three years [7]. The providers should advise that the risk factors and adverse effects of treatment on the patient, like a combination of chemotherapy drugs, cause nausea and vomiting. Hypothyroidism may be brought on by radiation to the neck and mediastinum [21]. After the treatment, some people may feel differently, like they were disease-free, but being worried about future cancer coming back is very common. So, the patients must undergo the follow-up as suggested by the doctors. The patient needs time to regain or rebuild their mental and emotional health, including their physical health. The healthcare providers advise you to recover and be in good health. The patient can make progress toward recovery with the support of a balanced diet and a healthy lifestyle. It may help to manage the late therapy side effects and could potentially lower the chance of some cancer remissions and other illnesses, such as heart disease, diabetes, and strokes [18,20].

Evaluation

- CBC, or complete blood count: number of RBC, WBC, and platelets in blood
- The test for lactate dehydrogenase (LDH): for tissue damage brought on by illness or accident
- The CMP, or comprehensive metabolic panel: kidney function, liver, and electrolytes in blood that regulate muscle and nerve activity
- Test for uric acid level: waste product in the bloodstream
- Biopsy and aspiration of the bone marrow: a sample of bone marrow for cancer cells
- A computed tomography CT scan: certain X-rays and a three-dimensional picture of the bones and soft tissues
- Positron emission tomography (PET) scans—pictures of tissues and organs in action
- Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD): signs of GI upper tract towards mantle cell lymphoma
- Colonoscopy: indicators of the big intestine (rectum and colon)

The above information concerning the genetic composition of the illness can be analyzed by tissue and blood samples, and for treatment plans, providers should understand the mutations.

Conclusion

MCL is called sporadic but is also often a straightforward diagnosis, yet confirming FISH investigations will avoid misinterpretation because morphologic variants may resemble other lymphoid neoplasms with a low threshold. The prognosis for patients with MCL, a malignant lymphoma, has significantly improved in both younger and older patients. Mantle cell lymphomas are a collection of diverse B-cell lymphomas with particular pathological traits [21]. This disorder can be managed by a medical oncologist, radiologist, team for bone marrow transplantation and radiation oncologist, expert surgeon, hematologist, clinical trial team, and expert nursing staff. The lethargic version of MCL that may need to be monitored with aggressive second-line therapy must be identified. This includes understanding the problems and side effects associated with these MCL treatments, which can aid in the effective management of MCL disorders in patients.

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